

Synthesis and spectral studies of some novel first transition metal complexes with 1-amidino-3-aryl- substituted- thioureas

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A series of complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II} and Zn^{II} with the amidinothioureas phenylamidinothiourea (PATU), *p*-tolylamidinothiourea (PTATU), *p*-chlorophenylamidinothiourea (PCATU) and *p*-anisylamidinothiourea (PAATU) have been prepared. Complexes are formed by the ligands in the thiol form after deprotonation and they are neutral. The electrochemical behavior of the complexes is followed using cyclic voltammetry and it is seen that the metal-sulfur linkage is having more covalent nature. The copper complex is square-planar, the cobalt and iron complexes are octahedral, the oxovanadium complexes are square-pyramidal and the zinc complexes are tetrahedral. The complexes show more antibacterial activity than the ligands.

A good number of amidinothioures with varying substituents at different positions are reported by several workers¹. However, coordination chemistry of these compounds are less studied. The thiol-thio keto tautomerism of amidinothioureas is well established². So there are different possibilities for complex formation. Though various donor sites are present in the ligands, they predominantly function as SN donor ligands in the thiol form.

Here we report some new complexes of the ligands (L) 1-amidino-3-aryl-thioureas (aryl = phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-anisyl) with Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II} and Zn^{II}.

Results and discussion

Copper, zinc and vanadyl complexes show a 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio (ML₂) while iron and cobalt show a 1 : 3 ratio (ML₃). The molar conductance data (19–26 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) observed in acetonitrile and methanol show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes. The magnetic moments of the copper complexes (1.73–1.83 B.M.) show that they are paramagnetic. The values of cobalt complexes (4.90–5.04 B.M.) and the iron complexes (~5.8 B.M.) are characteristic of high-spin octahedral complexes. The values of vanadyl complexes (1.74–1.81 B.M.) are the typical spin-only value of an unpaired electron. The zinc complexes are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra : The copper complexes show band at 430–448 nm, attributed to charge transfer spectrum and

another at 702–710 nm assignable to the three overlapping *d-d* transitions³ ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. The band for all the cobalt complexes seen at 550 nm, is attributed to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition characteristic of high-spin octahedral complexes of Co^{II}. All the Fe^{III} complexes have a weak absorption around 490 nm, which may be due to the spin-forbidden transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$. The vanadyl complexes have transitions around 600 and 750 nm, which are very weak, whereas the transition around 440 nm is comparatively strong due to the overlapping of the charge transfer spectra. The zinc complexes do not have any absorption apart from the absorptions of the ligands.

Infrared spectra : The ligands and complexes show strong bands at 3450–3160 cm⁻¹, assigned to the ν_{sym} and ν_{asym} of the NH and NH₂ groups⁴. The bands at 2350 and 1250 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the stretching and bending vibrations of the S–H group present in the thiol form of the ligand⁵. However, these frequencies are absent in the complexes of Cu, Fe, V and Zn, indicating formation of these complexes from the thiol form of the ligands after deprotonation.

The ligands band at 1070 cm⁻¹ (C=S of thione form)⁶ disappears in the complexes of Cu, Fe, V and Zn. This also confirms that the complexes are formed from the ligands in their thiol forms. The ligands band at 760 cm⁻¹ (C–S) is shifted (~40 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes⁷, indicating involvement of the sulfur atom on complexation.

The ligands bands around 1640 cm^{-1} (C=N), are retained in the spectra of the complexes. However, the complexes present a new band at $1625\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This can be assigned to the vibration of a C=N group which takes part in complexation¹. Again the metal-nitrogen bonds are indicated by the absorptions³ at 450 cm^{-1} . From the IR data, it can be inferred that the amidinothioureas function as monoanionic bidentate ligands coordinating through their thiol sulfur after deprotonation and an azomethine N atom.

The cobalt complexes retained the ligand band at 1070 cm^{-1} characteristic of C=S group of the thione form. In conjunction with the analytical data, it can be inferred that one of the ligands in the cobalt complexes is coordinated in the thione form without deprotonation.

All the complexes show bands due to the metal-nitrogen and metal-sulfur bonds.

Cyclic voltammetry: The cyclic voltammetric profile of the complexes was followed using a three-electrode system with glassy carbon as the working electrode, Pt as auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was used as the supporting electrode and ferrocene as the internal standard. Scanning was done at the rate of 100 mV/s in the range $+2000$ to -2000 mV . Only quasireversible peaks are seen. This may be due to the added covalency of the metal-sulfur bond⁸. The CV profile of $\text{Cu}(\text{PTATU})_2$ is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of $\text{Cu}(\text{PTATU})_2$.

ESR spectra: The X-band ESR spectra of the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{PATU})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{PCATU})_2$ at room temperature in solid state recorded at a frequency of 9.21 GHz with a field set of 3000 G are characteristic of axial symmetry ($g_x = g_y \neq g_z$)⁹. Hyperfine splitting is seen in the parallel component (four lines) and no splitting in the perpendicular component. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and g_{av} calculated are respectively 2.436,

2.052 and 2.18 for $\text{Cu}(\text{PATU})_2$ and 2.3761, 2.1134 and 2.2009 for $\text{Cu}(\text{PCATU})_2$. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0036) shows that the unpaired electron of the complex is localized in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the copper atom in both complexes¹⁰. The perpendicular component shows no hyperfine splitting and hence $A_{\perp} \approx 0$. A_{\parallel} values are 77.41 G for the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{PATU})_2$ and 59.94 G for the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{PCATU})_2$.

The ESR spectrum of $\text{VO}(\text{PTATU})_2$ at room temperature in solid state recorded at frequency of 9.22 GHz and field set of 2500 G exhibited axial symmetry with hyperfine splitting in both parallel and perpendicular components with partial overlap. The g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and g_{av} values calculated are 1.9212, 1.995 and 1.9704, respectively, A_{\parallel} is 157 G and A_{\perp} is 114 G . The trend $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_e$ shows that the unpaired electron is in the d_{xy} orbital of the VO^{II} ion¹¹.

Based on the above discussion, it can be seen that the amidinothioureas function as monoanionic, bidentate ligands. The copper complexes have a square-planar geometry and the cobalt complexes an octahedral geometry. The analytical data and IR data in tandem show that, of the three ligands, two are complexed in the thiol form after deprotonation and the third ligand is in the thione form. The nonelectrolytic behavior of the cobalt complexes can be explained on the basis of this structure. The iron complexes have an octahedral geometry. The experimental data for the vanadyl complexes show that they are square-pyramidal. The zinc complex can be considered to have a tetrahedral geometry.

Antibacterial activity: The ligand *p*-chlorophenylamidinothiourea (PCATU) and its complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity by the reported method¹² against *Staphylococcus aureus* in the concentration range $5\text{--}15\text{ }\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration. In all the concentrations, the ligand exhibits lower antibacterial activity than the complexes.

Experimental

The amidinothioureas were prepared by the reaction of guanidine carbonate with the appropriate isothiocyanate in presence of an alkali¹³.

The complexes. General method: To a boiling solution of the ligand in methanol (pH~7), a solution of the metal salt in aqueous methanol was added. Metal-ligand ratio was maintained at 1 : 2 or 1 : 3 with the metal in slight excess. There was a sudden colour change indicating the formation of the complex. The solvent (methanol) was removed by distillation, and the resulting solid complex was washed with water and crystallized from methanol or acetone.

C, H, N were analyzed by the microanalytical technique. Metal and sulfur were estimated gravimetrically. Conductance was measured on a Control Dynamics APX

Note

185 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. The electronic spectra (methanol) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT IR spectrophotometer and ESR spectra on a Jeol JM FE3 X-band spectrometer. Cyclic voltammetric studies of a few complexes were done in deaerated DMSO solution on a Cypress Inc. System machine.

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